

Financial Literacy Improvement Strategies in Supporting Financial Inclusion Policy in Gorontalo District

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Abstract:- Several studies have found evidence that individuals' attitudes toward finances are related to their spending habits, financial practices, and behaviors. This is identical to the habits of people who tend to be consumptive and have the habit of shopping and allocating their money for short-term things. This phenomenon shows that in-depth knowledge of financial literacy makes financial literacy education indispensable to educate people who are aware and understand how to manage finances wisely and according to their needs. This research was carried out by involving Youth Organizations in 191 villages in Gorontalo Regency. This research is a type of phenomenological research with a qualitative approach. Data was collected by using observation, interview and documentation methods. The results of the study found that knowledge about financial literacy has not been maximized. Especially in accessing and using the services and products offered/provided by financial institutions such as banks, financial institutions (finance) and pawnshops. Knowledge of financial inclusion is limited to the types of services in the form of transfers and payment transactions using online mode. As for product knowledge, respondents only know about products in the form of Savings and Current Accounts as well as loan products. Meanwhile, the products and services provided/offered by financial institutions are quite a lot in accordance with the types of activities/transactions needed by the community.

Keywords:- Financial Literacy; Financial Inclusion.

I. INTRODUCTION

Financial management has a very important role in determining the level of individual and family welfare. According to S. Rapih that literacy education for youth needs to be developed, especially financial literacy for individuals/families whose patterns of financial knowledge come from inadequate financial knowledge and are physically related to individual and family health (in Norvilitis, Szablicki, & Wilson, 2003). Other conditions that can increase the family's financial burden are economic decisions to increase consumer debt and the risk of bankruptcy (Lyons & Hunt, 2003), loss of savings and investments for retirement, and unwise financial management (Allen, Edwards, Hayhoe, & Leach, 2007).

In line with this, the ability to manage finances is very important whether it is applied to daily life or to be used in dealing with crisis situations that can occur at any time. The ability to manage finances is also very necessary to prepare for the necessities of life in the future. To meet the needs, including daily needs, the need for health, children's educational needs and the need for insurance in old age, a mature and well-planned financial management is needed.

Several studies have found evidence that individuals' attitudes toward finances are related to their spending habits, financial practices, and behavior (Rapih, 2016). This is identical to the habits of people who tend to be consumptive and have the habit of shopping and allocating their money for short-term things. In addition, the habits of the Indonesian people in carrying out consumption activities usually make purchases of goods based on their preference and interest in models of goods that look attractive, make purchases of goods without planning, buy goods based on price considerations and do not consider benefits or uses, buy goods at low prices. expensive goods or goods with well-known brands will lead to high self-confidence, buy goods of the same type but from different brands, buy goods to maintain their appearance and prestige, and buy goods to maintain status symbols (Astuti, 2013).

Judging from the importance of in-depth knowledge of financial literacy, financial literacy education is very necessary to educate people who are aware and understand how to manage finances wisely and according to their needs. Financial literacy education must be provided as soon as possible because there have been many cases of fraudulent investments that have harmed the community. Karanga cadet youth as part of the community need to strengthen their knowledge in the financial sector so they are not trapped in the fake investment structure. There are many investment cases in Indonesia, especially in the Gorontalo Region, which have ended up wrapped around the necks of the people themselves because it turns out that this investment does not have a strong and clear capital structure foundation.

Youth youth who are targeted in this literacy improvement because they are considered to have the sensitivity to read the situation and investment opportunities. Besides that, youth are also the foremost pioneers in moving the village economy. Based on the above background, researchers need to conduct research with the topic "Strategies for improving Financial literacy in Supporting

Financial Inclusion Policies in Gorontalo Regency". This research was conducted in villages in Gorontalo district which are included in the Tomini Bay area. Furthermore, research greatly supports the achievement of the strategic plan of the State University of Gorontalo so that it can improve the Main Performance Indicators of the Faculty of Economics.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Financial Inclusive

Financial inclusion is the provision of access to financial services for the entire population, especially the poor and other isolated populations. Everyone has the right to get access and full services from financial institutions in a convenient, informative, affordable and timely manner, without discrimination and full respect for their dignity. These services are provided to mostly disadvantaged and low-income groups.

World Bank describes financial inclusion as the range, quality and limitations of financial services for underserved and excluded finance for underserved and excluded finance. In the 2014 Global Financial Development Report, the World Bank also explains that financial inclusion is a condition in which most people can take advantage of available financial services and provide education to community groups who are not aware of the benefits of access to finance through access that is available without high costs.

B. Financial Inclusion Vision and Target

The national vision of inclusive finance is formulated to create a financial system that is accessible to all levels of society to encourage economic growth, poverty alleviation, income distribution and the creation of financial system stability in Indonesia. The financial inclusion vision is outlined in the following objectives:

- Make the financial inclusion strategy part of the grand strategy of economic development, poverty alleviation, income distribution and financial system stability. Inclusive finance is a strategy to achieve broader economic development goals, namely poverty alleviation and improving people's welfare, as well as part of a strategy to achieve financial system stability. The poor and marginalized are groups that have limited access to financial services. The objective of inclusive finance is to provide access to a wider range of financial services for

every citizen, but there is a need to give greater focus to the poor.

- Provide financial services and products in accordance with the needs of the community. The concept of inclusive finance must be able to meet all the different needs of different segments of the population through a comprehensive set of holistic services
- Increase public knowledge about financial services. The main obstacle to financial inclusion is the low level of financial knowledge. This knowledge is important so that people feel safer interacting with financial institutions.
- Increase public access to financial services. Barriers for the poor to access financial services are generally geographical and administrative constraints. Resolving these problems will be a fundamental breakthrough in simplifying access to financial services.
- Strengthening the synergy between banks, microfinance institutions, and non-bank financial institutions. The government must ensure not only the empowerment of branch offices, but also regulations that allow for the expansion of formal financial services. Therefore, the synergy between Banks, Microfinance Institutions (MFIs), and Non-Bank Financial Institutions is especially important in supporting the achievement of financial system stability.
- Optimizing the role of information and communication technology (ICT) to expand the scope of financial services. Technology can reduce transaction costs and expand the formal financial system beyond just savings and credit services. However, clear guidelines and regulations need to be established to balance the extent of coverage and risks.

C. National Framework for Inclusive Finance

World Bank (2010) revealed that there are at least four types of financial services that are considered vital for people's lives, namely fund storage services, credit services, payment system services and insurance, including pension funds. These four aspects are the basic requirements that every community must have in order to obtain a better life. Increasing public access to financial institutions is certainly a problem of complexity that requires cross-sectoral coordination involving banking authorities, non-bank financial services and other ministries or institutions that pay attention to poverty alleviation efforts, so that a comprehensive and comprehensive policy is needed in a National Strategy for Financial Inclusion.

The complete framework for the National Strategy for Financial Inclusion (SNKI) can be seen in the following graph:

Graph 1:- Framework for the National Strategy for Financial Inclusion

D. Financial Literacy

The development of the financial services industry is increasing and increasingly complex, thereby changing financial market conditions. Therefore, one needs to understand basic financial knowledge related to the keys to modern financial security (Mandell & Klein, 2007: 105). This knowledge is absolutely needed by every individual in order to optimally utilize financial instruments and products in order to make the right decisions for their welfare. As stated by ASIC (2013: 6) that financial literacy can help someone to make better financial decisions and get more profits.

According to Lisa Xu and Bilal Zia (2012) said that the term financial literacy includes concepts that start from awareness and understanding of financial products, financial terms, and concepts regarding financial skills such as the ability to calculate compound interest payments as well as more general financial abilities such as money management and financial planning. Lusardi (2012) states that financial literacy is a skill that is mastered by every individual to improve their standard of living by understanding the planning and allocation of appropriate and efficient financial resources. In addition, Huston (2010) defines financial literacy as the expertise possessed by individuals with the ability to manage their income in order to achieve an increase in financial welfare. Financial literacy is the basic thing that must be understood and mastered by every individual because it affects a person's financial condition and has an impact on making good and appropriate economic decisions (Anggraeni, 2015).

III. METHOD

This research was carried out by involving Youth Organizations in Gorontalo Regency. Geographically, Gorontalo Regency has 19 sub-districts, 14 sub-districts and 191 villages. The locus of this research is focused on Youth Organizations located on the coast of Gorontalo Regency which consists of Batudaa Pantai District, Bilato District and Biluhu District. This research is a type of phenomenological research where the researcher must have a broad view and try to understand the meaning of events and their relation to objects in certain situations. The approach used is qualitative where the researcher intends to collect information about the status of an existing symptom.

Data was collected by using observation, interview and documentation methods. Data analysis technique. The data analysis process involves a way to understand data in the form of text and data in the form of images which then prepares the data to be used for analysis and comprehensively and in detail to be able to understand the data so that the interpretation of the data is deeper and measurable (Creswell, 2009). The data analysis technique used is the interactive model of Miles et al., (2014), namely the analysis carried out in the form of three components, namely data reduction, data presentation and verification/drawing conclusions. The three components in question take place continuously until they are complete, so that the data is saturated. The size of the data saturation is indicated by the absence of new data or information.

IV.RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Overview of Research Objects

Gorontalo Regency is one of the regencies in Gorontalo Province. This district was formed by Law Number 29 of 1959 concerning the Establishment of Level II Regions in Sulawesi with the capital city in Isimu. The district capital of Gorontalo was then moved from Isimu to Limboto. Gorontalo Regency's birthday was set on November 26, 1973 based on the signing of an agreement from the u'dulowo limo lo pohalaa family ties

consisting of the Gorontalo Kingdom, Limboto Kingdom, Suwawa Kingdom, Boalemo Kingdom and Atinggola Kingdom (gorontalokab.go.id, 2022).

The area of Gorontalo Regency is 1,750.83 km² with a population of 395,635 people. When compared with the total population of Gorontalo Province which amounted to 1,180,948 people, the population of Gorontalo Regency is the largest in the province, which is 33.50%. Gorontalo Regency currently has 19 sub-districts as follows:

No	District	Area	Village	Village Center
1	Asparaga	534,99	10 Village	Karya Indah
2	Tolangohula	149,30	15 Village	Suka Makmur
3	Mootilango	185,39	10 Village	Paris
4	Boliyohuto	60,59	13 Village	Sidomulyo
5	Bilato	112,34	10 Village	Totopo
6	Pulubala	247,04	11 Village	Pulubala
7	Tibawa	137,56	16 Village	Isimu Selatan
8	Limboto Barat	93,35	10 Village	Huidu
9	Limboto	86,61	14 Village	Kayubulan
10	Telaga Biru	57,86	15 Village	Tuladenggi
11	Telaga	100,47	9 Village	Luhu
12	Telaga Jaya	4,98	5 Village	Luwoo
13	Tilango	5,15	8 Village	Tilote
14	Batudaa	208,23	8 Village	Payunga
15	Batudaa Pantai	50,58	9 Village	Kayubulan
16	Biluhu	99,03	8 Village	Lobuto Timur
17	Bongomeme	114,16	15 Village	Dulamayo
18	Tabongo	36,34	9 Village	Tabongo Timur
19	Dungaliyo	46,62	10 Village	Dungaliyo

Table 1:- Number of Districts in Gorontalo 2022
Source: Gorontalo Regency Government, 2022

This research was conducted in a sub-district located on the coast of Gorontalo Regency. Based on table 1, the number of sub-districts located on the coast of Gorontalo Regency is Batudaa Pantai District which consists of 9 villages, Bilato District which consists of 10 villages and Biluhu District which consists of 8 villages. The focus of this research was conducted on the managers of youth organizations scattered in the sub-districts on the coast of Gorontalo Regency. Research interviews were conducted on 56 youth leaders and managers in the three sub-districts.

B. Characteristics of Respondents

➤ Characteristics of Respondents by Gender

Based on the results of research conducted on coastal youth organizations in Gorontalo Regency which consists of Batudaa Pantai sub-district, Bilato sub-district and Biluhu sub-district in Gorontalo district, the characteristics of respondents based on gender can be seen in fig 1 below:

Fig 1:- Characteristics of Respondents by Gender (Source: Processed Data, 2022)

In Figure 1 it can be seen that the percentage of respondents with male gender is 78% or as many as 42 people, while respondents with female sex are 22% or as many as 12 people. This shows that the managers of youth organizations in Batudaa Pantai, Bilato and Biluhu sub-districts are dominated by men.

➤ Characteristics of Respondents Based on Age

Based on interviews with youth managers in the Subdistricts, Batudaa Pantai, Bilato Subdistricts and Biluhu Subdistricts, the characteristics of respondents based on age can be seen in Figure 2 below:

Fig 2:- Characteristics of Respondents by Age (Source: Processed Data, 2022)

In Figure 2 it can be seen that the percentage of respondents aged 15 to 25 years is 43% or as many as 23 people, respondents aged 26 to 35 years is 37% or as many as 20 people, respondents aged 36 to 45 years is 9% or as many as 5 people and respondents aged over 45 years are 11% or as many as 6 people. This shows that the youth organizations in

Batudaa Pantai, Bilato and Biluhu sub-districts are dominated by an average age of 15 to 25 years.

➤ Characteristics of Respondents Based on Education Level

Based on interviews with youth organizations in the sub-districts of Batudaa Pantai, Bilato sub-district and Biluhu sub-district, the characteristics of respondents based on education level can be seen in Figure 3 below:

Fig 3:- Characteristics of Respondents Based on Education Level (Source: Processed Data, 2022)

In Figure 3 it can be seen that the percentage of respondents with a junior high school education level (SMP) is 6% or as many as 3 people, respondents with a high school education level (SMA) is 31% or as many as 17 people and respondents with education up to at the university level is 63% or as many as 34 people. This shows that the managers of youth organizations in Batudaa Pantai, Bilato and Biluhu sub-districts are dominated by managers whose education level is up to university.

➤ Characteristics of Respondents Based on Financial Product Ownership

Based on interviews with youth organizations in the District, Batudaa Pantai, Bilato District and Biluhu District, the characteristics of the respondents based on the type of respondent's ownership of the products available in financial institutions, both bank/finance/pawnshops, can be seen in Figure 4 below:

Fig 4:- Characteristics of Respondents by Type of Ownership of Financial Institution Products (Source: Processed Data, 2022)

In Figure 4 it can be seen that the percentage of respondents who have financial institution products in the form of Savings is 80% or as many as 43 people, respondents who have financial institution products in the form of Current Accounts are 9% or as many as 5 people and respondents who have financial institution products in the form of Loans/Credits is 11% or as many as 6 people. This shows that the ownership of the youth organization's

management of the products offered by financial institutions such as banks/finance/pawnshops is dominated by ownership of products in the form of savings.

➤ Education Level of Respondents at Age 15 – 25 Years

Based on the results of the study, respondents who have a certain level of education in the 15-25 year age group can be seen in Figure 5 below:

Fig 5:- Education Level of Respondents Age Range 15-25 Years (Source: Processed Data, 2022)

Based on Figure 5, it can be seen that in the age range of 15 to 25 years, it was found that 22% of the respondents had an education level up to the college level and 20% of the respondents had an education level at the high school level. Meanwhile, respondents who have an education level at the junior high school level are not found in the age range of 15 to 25 years in this study.

➤ Education Level of Respondents at the Age of 26 - 35 Years

Based on the results of the study, respondents who have a certain level of education in the age group of 26-35 years can be seen in Figure 6, as follows:

Fig 6:- Education Level of Respondents Age Range 26 - 35 Years (Source: Processed Data, 2022)

➤ Education Level of Respondents at the Age of 36 – 45 Years

Based on the results of the study, respondents who have a certain level of education in the 36-45 year age group can be seen in Figure 7 below:

Fig 7:- Education Level of Respondents Age Range 36 – 45 Years (Source: Processed Data, 2022)

Based on Figure 7, it can be seen that in the age range of 36 - 45 years, it was found that 7% of the respondents had an education level up to college level and 2% of respondents had an education level at the high school level. Meanwhile, respondents who have an education level at the junior high school level are not found in the age range of 36 to 45 years in this study.

➤ Education Level of Respondents over 45 Years Old

Based on the results of the study, respondents who have a certain level of education in the age group > 45 years can be seen in Figure 8 below:

Fig 8:- Education Level of Respondents Age Range 36 – 45 Years (Source: Processed Data, 2022)

Based on Figure 8, it can be seen that in the age range >45 years, it was found that 4% of respondents had an education level up to the college level, 2% of respondents had an education level at the high school level and 6% of respondents had an education level at the junior high school level.

The results of this study indicate that the managers of youth organizations in Batudaa Pantai sub-district, Bilato sub-district and Biluhu sub-district in Gorontalo district have a high level of education. Based on Figure 5, Figure 6, Figure 7 and Figure 8, it can be seen that the highest level of education in the three sub-districts is in the age range of 15-25 years with a percentage of 22% and in the age range of 26-35 years, which is 30% of the total respondents. . This shows

that people are aware of the importance of education. Public understanding of the level of financial literacy and financial inclusion is strongly supported by the level of education, especially at the productive age. Higher education in general can support knowledge about financial literacy and financial inclusion.

C. Product Ownership of Financial Institutions based on Respondent Age

➤ *Product Ownership of Financial Institutions at the Age of 15 - 25 Years*

Based on the results of the study, respondents who have products from financial institutions, either bank/finance/pawnshops in the age group 15> 25 years can be seen in Figure 9 below;

Fig 9:- Product Ownership of Financial Institutions in the Age Range 15 – 25 Years (Source: Processed Data, 2022)

Figure 9 shows that respondents who have financial institution products, either bank/finance/pawnshops in the form of savings in the age range 15-25 are 37%, products in the form of demand deposits 2% and financial institution products in the form of credit as much as 4%. In Figure 9, it can be seen that products in the form of savings are the most popular financial institution products in the 15-25 year age range.

➤ *Product Ownership of Financial Institutions at the Age of 26 - 35 Years*

Based on the results of the study, respondents who have products from financial institutions, both bank/finance/pawnshops in the age group of 26> 35 years can be seen in Figure 10 below:

Fig 10:- Product Ownership of Financial Institutions in the Age Range 26 - 35 Years (Source: Processed Data, 2022)

Figure 10 shows that respondents who have products from financial institutions, either bank/finance/pawnshops in the form of savings in the age range 26 - 35 are 26%, products in the form of demand deposits 7% and financial institution

products in the form of credit as much as 4%. In Figure 10, it can be seen that products in the form of savings are the most popular products of financial institutions in the age range of 26-35 years.

D. Discussion

➤ Knowledge of Youth Organization Managers About Financial Literacy

• Investment

The results showed that 52% of youth organizations in the three sub-districts understood investment practices. This means that most managers have heard or know about investment activities and the objectives of these investment activities. One of the investment activities referred to is by buying or using products offered by financial institutions in the form of savings, current accounts or deposits or investments in gold and other real assets.

• How to invest

The results of the study show that 41% of youth organizations in three sub-districts understand how to invest properly. However, in this study it was found that 30% of managers did not understand how to invest properly and correctly. This needs to be followed up to minimize actions that are detrimental to the community, especially in investment practices.

• Desire to invest

This study shows the results that the manager's interest in investing is 41%. This means that most of the youth organizations in the three sub-districts located on the coast of Gorontalo Regency have a desire to invest, while 39% are hesitant to invest. If it is seen from the percentage of managers who feel hesitant to invest, it can be said that this is reasonable, considering that in the last few years, there has been a lot of fraud under the guise of investment. The government in this case needs to be aware of these fraudulent investment practices. This can be done by providing an understanding to the public about what investment is and how to invest properly and correctly.

• Investment risk

The results of the research show that 31% of managers know/understand and 31% really know/understand the risks that may be experienced when conducting investment activities. Meanwhile, 30% of managers are unsure about the risks that may be experienced. This is often found among the people of Indonesia, where many want the benefits of an investment, but are not ready with the risks that may be accepted.

• How to manage finances

The results showed that 65% of managers already know/understand how to manage finances properly and correctly and can do it properly. In this case, the government needs to follow up on this matter, so that active investment in the three sub-districts studied can be maximized.

• Benefits of good and correct financial management

The results showed that 67% of youth organizations in three sub-districts located on the coast of Gorontalo Regency knew and understood the benefits of good and correct financial management.

• Good and correct financial management

The results showed that 67% of managers who know/understand the benefits of good and correct financial management can realize it in the form of financial management. 67% of managers in this study have managed their finances properly and correctly. If this can be maximized by the Gorontalo Regency government, especially the government in the three sub-districts, it can improve the economy in the area.

• Requirements for obtaining a loan from a financial institution

The results showed that 59% of youth organizations in the three sub-districts where the research was located knew/understood the requirements set by financial institutions in obtaining capital assistance in the form of these loans. However, there are 29% managers who do not know/understand about this.

• Products offered by financial institutions

This study shows that only 33% of managers know/understand the types of products offered by financial institutions. However, in this study it was also found that there are 50% of youth managers in three sub-districts on the coast of Gorontalo Regency who do not know/understand the products offered by financial institutions.

• Benefits of deposit products offered by financial institutions

The results of this study indicate that 37% of youth organizations in three sub-districts know/understand the benefits of this type of product in the form of savings. However, it was also found in this study that 43% of managers do not know/understand the benefits of savings products offered by financial institutions.

• Benefits of loan products offered by financial institutions

According to financial institutions, all forms of loans are beneficial to the community. However, in this study it was found that only 35% of youth organizations knew/understand the benefits of loan products offered by financial institutions. There are still 41% managers who do not know/understand the benefits of the loan products offered.

• Analyze financial condition regularly every day/week/month/year

The results of this study indicate that 46% of managers always analyze their financial condition periodically. However, there are 46% of managers who do not know/understand and carry out the process of analyzing the financial condition.

• Knowledge of financial literacy

This study shows that only 37% of managers know/understand the concept of financial literacy. Meanwhile, more than 44% of the community in this case are youth managers who do not know/understand about financial literacy.

- Expenditure according to need

The results of this study indicate that there are 52% of youth managers who have been able to streamline the level of expenditure. However, there are still 24% of managers who are not able to carry out this efficiency.

- Planning in financial management

The results of this study indicate that 70% of managers have been able to plan in financial management. Meanwhile, only 11% of youth organizations did not do financial management planning.

- Control expenses incurred

The results of this study indicate that the cadets in three sub-districts located on the coast of Gorontalo Regency are quite good at controlling the costs incurred. This can be seen from 67% of youth organizations who can control the costs incurred in managing their finances.

- Good planning can minimize risk

The results of this study indicate that more than 52% of managers know/understand that good planning in financial management can minimize the level of risk posed, including risk in terms of investment.

- Ownership of deposit products in financial institutions

The results of this study indicate that only 28% of managers use financial institution products in the form of savings. Meanwhile, 33% of youth organizations have not used these savings products. In general, managers have deposit products only for payment traffic. The function of savings as a form of investment is not found in this study. People use savings, especially savings, which are intended to facilitate buying and selling transactions which currently predominantly use online payment methods.

- Use of credit at financial institutions

The results of this study indicate that 41% of youth organizations in three sub-districts in Gorontalo Regency use financial institution products in the form of loans or credit. Most of these managers use loan facilities for business capital.

Based on the results of the research above, it can be concluded that in general the managers of youth organizations in Batudaa Pantai District, Bilato District and Biluhu District which are located on the coast of Gorontalo Regency understand and understand investment and financial management. However, there are still a small number of managers who do not understand and understand this. Investment activity and financial management in Gorontalo Regency need to be improved. The development of the Tomini Bay area, especially in the coastal area, is very necessary. Especially with the rise of illegal investment mechanisms that have developed in the community in recent years. Pohuwato Regency and Boalemo Regency, where many people are deceived by illegal investment practices, need attention. This is intended so that illegal investment practices can be avoided, especially in the Gorontalo Regency area.

- Knowledge of Youth Organization Managers About Financial Inclusion

- Knowledge of official/legal financial institutions such as bank/finance/pawnshop

The results of this study indicate that more than 56% of the youth organizations in Batudaa Pantai, Bilato and Biluhu sub-districts know and understand these financial institutions. Meanwhile, the number of people who do not know/understand about these financial institutions is 11% - 17%.

- Knowledge of the types of services provided by financial institutions such as banks/finance/pawnshops

The results of this study indicate that the types of services provided by financial institutions are only limited to the types of products such as savings, current accounts and credit/loans. Other services such as deposit products, letter of credit services, safe deposit boxes and other modern services are not yet known by the public, especially youth organizations. This is evidenced by the level of public knowledge which only reached 39%. Meanwhile, 35% of the public do not even know/understand these products and services.

- Accessibility of financial services provided by financial institutions such as banks/finance/pawnshops

The results of the study show that 56% of youth organizations are aware, know and understand the accessibility of products and services from these financial institutions. This proves that there is increasing attention from financial institutions on the accessibility of financial institutions' products and services in the sub-districts of the research locations.

- Use of types of financial institution products such as bank/finance/pawnshops for needs and to manage finances

Based on the results of the study, it can be seen that more than 56% of youth organizations in these sub-districts have used the products and services provided/offered by financial institutions, although the use of these products and services is still limited to buying and selling transaction activities such as transfers or online payments.

- Use of the internet in accessing the services of financial institutions such as banks/finance/pawnshops

The results showed that more than 46% of managers were able to make transactions using internet facilities. Transfers and online payments can now be done without having to visit the location of these financial institutions.

- Guidance on how to use the services of financial institutions such as banks/finance/pawnshops

The results of this study indicate that more than 76% of youth organization managers know/understand how to access services, both services and products offered because of the complete guidelines and procedures available in various media, both offline and online.

- Affordable service fees for financial institutions such as banks/finance/pawnshops

This study shows that more than 57% of managers stated that the service fees charged by these financial institutions were still affordable by the community. This needs to be considered considering that currently almost all lines of life require services and products from financial institutions. Thus, the amount of fees that must be charged to the user needs to be considered so that it is easy to reach.

- Products provided by financial institutions such as banks/finance/pawnshops can increase income

The results showed that more than 57% of youth organizations in the sub-districts where the research was located stated that there was an increase in opinion as a positive impact of using the services and products provided/offered by these financial institutions.

Based on the results of the research above, it is necessary to pay attention from the government and financial institutions to aspects of accessibility, strategic location, service fees that will be charged to the community and support for increasing people's income through the role of financial institutions. The easier it is to access the existence of financial institutions supported by adequate facilities and low costs, then this can increase people's income.

V. CONCLUSION

The knowledge of youth managers in Batudaa Pantai District, Bilato District and Biluhu District on the coast of Gorontalo Regency about financial literacy can be said to be good. However, knowledge about financial literacy has not been maximized. Especially in accessing and using the services and products offered/provided by financial institutions such as banks, financial institutions (finance) and pawnshops. The knowledge of youth managers in the three sub-districts about financial inclusion is limited to the types of services in the form of transfers and online transaction payments. As for product knowledge, the manager only knows about products in the form of Savings and Current Accounts as well as loan products. Meanwhile, the products and services provided/offered by financial institutions are quite a lot in accordance with the types of activities/transactions needed by the community.

RECOMMENDATION

The government and financial institutions are expected to synergize to increase public knowledge about financial inclusion and financial literacy. Official and legal investment practices can be carried out by the community if they have sufficient knowledge about public financial literacy. The government and financial institutions are expected to carry out socialization and provide adequate access, especially to financial inclusion in Batudaa Pantai District, Bilato District and Biluhu District, Gorontalo Regency.

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